

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824323

This document reflects only the views of the author(s). Neither the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA) nor the European Commission is in any way responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

European forum and oBsErVatory for OPEN science in transport

Project Acronym: **BE OPEN**

Project Title: **European forum and oBsErVatory for OPEN science in transport**

Project Number: **824323**

Topic: **MG-4-2-2018 – Building Open Science platforms in transport research**

Type of Action: **Coordination and support action (CSA)**

D6.3 Project leaflet

Final

Deliverable Title:	D6.3 Project leaflet
Work Package:	WP6: Dissemination and Engagement
Due Date:	M6
Submission Date:	M6
Start Date of Project:	01/01/2019
Duration of Project:	30 months
Organisation Responsible of Deliverable:	ECTRI
Version:	1.0
Status:	Final
Author name(s):	Ana Pereira (ECTRI), Caroline Alméras (ECTRI)
Reviewer(s):	Jakob Michelmann (VDE-VDI) and Armando Carrillo Zanuy (EURNEX)
Nature:	<input type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> P – Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> D – Demonstrator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> O - Other
Dissemination level:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history			
Version	Date	Modified by (author/partner)	Comments
0.1	14.05.2019	Ana Pereira (ECTRI)	1 st draft version, no figures
0.2	2.07.2019	Caroline Alméras (ECTRI)	Comments and completion based on final leaflet version
1.0	2.07.2019	Ana Pereira (ECTRI)	Adding figures and finalization

Executive summary

The present deliverable is part of the WP6 “Dissemination and Engagement”, Task 6.2 Dissemination Activities and events. It summarizes the development and implementation of the BE OPEN leaflet.

This document is divided in two sections. The Introduction, which briefly introduces the objectives of the WP6 “Dissemination and Engagement” and how the leaflet will contribute to it. The Section 2, “BE OPEN LEAFLET” presents and describes the BE OPEN leaflet, the development process and its main elements.

Disclaimer:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Table of contents

Executive summary	3
Table of contents.....	4
List of figures	4
Abbreviations	4
1 INTRODUCTION	5
2 BE OPEN LEAFLET	5
2.1 Purpose and usage	5
2.2 Content.....	6
2.2.1 Front page	6
2.2.2 Back page.....	7
3 REFERENCES	7

List of figures

Figure 1. BE OPEN leaflet front page.....	7
Figure 2. BE OPEN leaflet back page	7

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
CMS	Content Management System
T	Task
TOPOS	Transport Observatory/Forum for Promoting Open Science
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

The present deliverable is part of the WP6 “Dissemination and Engagement”[1], which has as key actions:

- Disseminate key project outputs to key actors and transport stakeholders;
- Implement and regularly update an appropriate online presence (web-site, social media, EOSC integration) and other relevant dissemination material to ensure continuous outreach of the project outcomes, as well as transfer of knowledge;
- Organise project key events and ensure cooperation with the most important international forums, as well as liaise with related projects and initiatives. Demonstrate the economic viability and lay the foundations for subsequent exploitation;
- Engage publishing companies and set up communication tools/actions;
- Supervise project results and key outcomes through an external Advisory Board, consisting of internationally renowned experts.

To create awareness and support the achievement of the project’s objectives, the consortium has defined under Task 6.2 Dissemination Activities and events [1], the development of several external communication tools, in which is included the BE OPEN leaflet. Together with the BE OPEN roll up banner, the leaflet will constitute the main offline dissemination tools.

2 BE OPEN LEAFLET

The BE OPEN leaflet is designed to serve as a “business card” of BE OPEN, providing “in a nutshell” key information about the project and in view to be used for promotional purpose among the targeted project audience.

Considering the main trends towards digital support for communication material, and progressive disappearance of hard support, together with diminishing interest from audience in printed material, it was decided to opt for a printed light eye-catching leaflet which would gather key messages and visuals to allow for readers both to capture the key information and essence of the BE OPEN project, and to find the main information for further engagement.

In this view, the leaflet’s structure is kept focused and concise, presenting the project’s main objectives, the partners involved and promoting the website and social media platforms and contact persons, as a source to incite the reader to look for more information and as an intent to join the community.

The leaflet follows the project identity (logo, colors and typography) to make a coherent link with the other communication tools. It is available in both printed and digital formats. The printed version is implemented in an A5 two-sided landscape format for ease of use, readability and carriage. The digital version is readable (and printable) in one A4 format.

2.1 Purpose and usage

The printed version of the leaflet serves to promote the project during conferences, workshops, networking events, face-to-face meetings and as permanent visual presence in the partner’s offices.

The consortium has planned to print and distribute 1,000 copies. Those copies will be kept within the coordinator CERTH-HIT and dissemination leader ECTRI. They will be made available to each Partner and sent to them on demand. More copies may be printed, if needs be, during the project.

The digital version of the leaflet serves for the dissemination of general project information to interested parties, stakeholders, the wider academic and industrial communities and the general public as an online tool available on the project website. The digital version is shared with all Partners via email, and made available for download at the [BE OPEN website](#) under publications and on the Partners area (Freedcamp tool).

2.2 Content

2.2.1 Front page

The front page presents the BE OPEN logo, the project’s full title, the objectives and overall goal and the projects online platforms, including a QR code for quick connection to the project website. The front page outlines the main goal of the BE OPEN project to “promote, regulate and standardize Open Science in Transport”. The visual aims at creating awareness for the reader on the main expected outcome of the project which is the setting up of the “TOPOS” e.g. “Transport Forum / Observatory for Promoting Open Science”. Each letter T. O. P. O. S are included in a round circle around the project’ objectives, as a process where each letter represent a step toward the final result, the “TOPOS”. The visual also brings the understanding that the TOPOS will be established

when all 5 objectives are implemented and reached.

Figure 1. BE OPEN leaflet front page

2.2.2 Back page

The back page includes all the Partners' logos and related Third Parties logos and present them as a team, the contact persons (coordinator and dissemination and engagement leader) and the acknowledgement of EU funding. It also reminds that the main funding scheme (CSA) and the duration of the project together with starting date (30 months, January 1st, 2019)

30-months H2020 Coordination & Support Action, started January 1st, 2019

The Team (Third Parties)

Project Coordinator: Maria Boile (CERTH-HIT) – Dissemination and Engagement Leader: Caroline Alméras (ECTRI) – beopenprojecteu@gmail.com

Promote, regulate and standardise
Open Science (OS) in Transport

The BE OPEN project has received funding from the
European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation
programme under grant agreement No 824323

Figure 2. BE OPEN leaflet back page

3 REFERENCES

[1] BE OPEN Grant Agreement